

Roll No.....

JC BOSE UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, YMCA FARIDABAD
Department of Communication and Media Technology
BSW Sessional-II Semester-III
Subject Name: Community Organization and Social Action (SWU-205-V)

Max. Marks-15

Time- 90 Minutes

- All questions are Compulsory in Part A
- Do any Two in the part B.
- Write clear and concise answers.

Part-A

- Q.1 (a) Define Social Action in Social Work. CO1
- (b) Mention any one model of Social Action. CO1
- (c) What is the main objective of the Bhoodan Movement? CO1
- (d) Name any one environmental movement in India. CO2
- (e) What does Sarvodaya mean? CO2

1X5=5

Part-B

- Q.1. Explain the relationship of Social Action with other methods of Social Work? CO2
2. Discuss the major principles and strategies of Social Action. CO1
3. Describe the important social movement in india such as Dalit, Women, and Environmental movements, Highlighting their significance.

CO1

5X2=10